

Electrochemical Synthesis of (Z)-11-Hexadecen-1-yl Acetate—the Pheromone of Purple Stem-borer (*Sesamia inferens*)

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(Z)-11-Hexadecen-1-yl acetate, the pheromone of purple stem-borer (*Sesamia inferens*) has been prepared in an overall good yield using cross Kolbe electro-synthesis as a key step.

(Z)-11-Hexadecen-1-yl acetate (9) is the pheromone of the purple stem-borer (*Sesamia inferens*), a noctuid moth whose larvae attack a wide range of graminaceous crops¹. This is also the pheromone of *Mamestra brassicae*². The synthesis of 9 has been carried out through the acetylenic route^{1,2}. Schäfer reported its preparation by co-electrolysing alkynoic acid with dicarboxylic monoester³. Here, we report the synthesis of 9 involving another electrochemical key step using cross Kolbe electrolysis of (Z)-4-nonenic acid (4) and azelaic acid monomethyl ester (5).

The reaction sequence involves the preparation of (Z)-4-nonenic acid (4) from γ -butyrolactone and hydrogen bromide followed by a step involving Wittig olefination⁴ (Scheme 1). Partially neutralised mixture of 4 and azelaic acid monomethyl ester (5) are electrolysed at smooth platinum electrodes in an undivided (without diaphragm) cell to afford methyl (Z)-11-hexadecenoate (6). Hydrolysis of 6 using ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave (Z)-11-hexadecenoic acid (7). Lithium aluminium hydride reduces 7 to (Z)-11-hexadecenol (8) which on acetylation with acetyl chloride-pyridine mixture finally afforded (Z)-11-hexadecen 1-yl acetate (9).

Experimental

Elemental microanalyses were obtained using CHN analyser Perkin Elmer 240, C. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a JEOL FT-NMR FX-90Q spectrometer and the chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to TMS (=0 ppm). γ -Butyrolactone, triphenylphosphine, valeraldehyde, sodium hydride, azelaic acid monomethyl ester and lithium aluminium hydride (all Aldrich) were used as such. Anhydrous hydrogen bromide was prepared from tetralin and bromine by a reported method⁵. Diethyl ether and dimethyl sulphoxide were dried following

known procedures⁶. The remaining chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade.

The electrolysis apparatus consisted of a double-wall cell (200 ml) closed with a teflon cover. Cold water was circulated through the cooling mantle to maintain the temperature of the electrolyte around 25°. Two smooth platinum electrodes each with surface area of 7 cm² were placed at a distance of 0.6 cm. Constant current was passed by a d.c. regulated power supply. The electrolyte was stirred magnetically.

(Z)-11-Hexadecenoic acid (7): (Z)-4-Nonenoic acid (0.78 g, 0.005 mol) and azelaic acid monomethyl ester (2.02 g, 0.01 mol), partially neutralised by potassium hydroxide (0.0672 g, 8% of acids neutralised) in methanol, were electrolysed at smooth platinum anode for 1.5 F current equivalent (current density 0.16 A cm⁻²). After the electrolysis (pH 8.0), the electrolyte was just neutralised with glacial acetic acid. Methanol was then removed at rotatory evaporator and the residue was taken into distilled water (20 ml). It was extracted with solvent ether (3×15 ml). The ethereal layer was successively washed with saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate (2×10 ml) and water (2×10 ml). The organic phase was placed over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and evaporated. The residue was saponified for 5 h with potassium hydroxide (5 g) in ethanol (20 ml). The solvent was evaporated and extracted with petroleum ether to remove the dimer formed by the one-electron electrolysis of acids. The residue was refluxed in ethanol for 2 h and filtered. The potassium salt of (Z)-11-hexadecenoic acid after distilling ethanol was dissolved in water and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to pH 1. It was extracted with solvent ether, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), filtered and evaporated to get 7 (0.58 g, 46%) (Found: C, 75.58; H, 11.83.

Scheme 1

$C_{18}H_{36}O$ requires: C, 75.59; H, 11.81%; ν_{max} (neat) 3 000–2 800 (OH), 1 708 (C=O) and 720 cm^{-1} (*cis*-double bond); $\delta(CCl_4)$ 12.0 (1H, s, CO₂H), 5.31 (2H, m, CH=CH), 2.33 (2H, t, CH₂CO), 1.98 (4H, m, CH₂C=), 1.25–1.7 (18H, br s, CH₂) and 0.92 (3H, t, CH₃).

(*Z*)-11-Hexadecen-1-ol (8): (*Z*)-11-Hexadecenoic acid (7; 0.306 g, 1.2 mmol) in absolute ether (5 ml) was added dropwise under ice-cooling condition to lithium aluminium hydride (0.34 g, 10 mmol) in absolute ether (20 ml) and then stirred for 5 h. The solution was then cautiously hydrolysed with water (2 ml) and to it were added 2*N* NaOH (1 ml) and water (1 ml) with ether. The hydroxide precipitate was filtered and washed with acetone (2×5 ml). It was again dried and washed with ether (3×10 ml). The combined organic phase was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the solvent evaporated at rotatory evaporator to afford 8 (0.278 g, 96%) (Found C, 79.97; H, 13.31. $C_{18}H_{36}O$ requires: C, 80.00; H, 13.33%; ν_{max} (neat) 3 400–2 900 (OH), 1 045 (C–O) and 720 cm^{-1} (*cis*-double bond); $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 5.33 (2H, t, CH=CH), 3.52 (3H, t, CH₂O+OH), 2.0 (4H, m,

CH₂C=), 1.15–1.56 (18H, s, CH₂) and 0.90 (3H, t, CH₃).

(*Z*)-11-Hexadecen-1-yl acetate (9): (*Z*)-11-Hexadecen-1-ol (8; 0.208 g, 0.86 mmol) in benzene (1 ml) was added dropwise under stirring and cooling condition to a cooled mixture of acetyl chloride (0.15 g) and pyridine (0.2 g) in benzene (1 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h and then decomposed with ether (20 ml) and water (4 ml). The organic phase was decanted, washed with 2*N* H₂SO₄ (2×10 ml), dried over potassium carbonate, filtered and the solvent removed at rotatory evaporator to afford 9 (0.240 g, 98.5%) (Found: C, 76.62; H, 12.03. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires: C, 76.59; H, 12.05%; ν_{max} (neat) 1 745 (C=O), 1 045 (C–O) and 720 cm^{-1} (*cis*-double bond); $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 5.28 (2H, t, CH=CH), 3.98 (2H, t, CH₂–O), 2.0 (7H, s, CH₂C=C+OCCH₃), 1.1–1.65 (18H, s, CH₂) and 0.90 (3H, t, CH₃).

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